

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Thermal Neutrons Effects on High-Level Synthesis Tools For Machine Learning</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-322</i>
General application	<i>High-reliability ground level, low power applications, accelerators</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Fernando Fernandes dos Santos, INRIA</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Marcello Traiola and Angeliki Kritikakou</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>17th December 2024</i>
Facility	<i>EMMA, ISIS</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>72 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have revolutionized many sectors, from user applications to self-driving cars and space exploration. To effectively deploy DNNs, powerful accelerators like Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are necessary. However, hardware design is often complex and requires using hardware description languages such as VHDL and Verilog, which can slow development. To simplify this process, High-Level Synthesis (HLS) tools have become popular as they enhance DNN acceleration on FPGAs.

FPGAs remain vulnerable to radiation-induced errors, which can affect DNN reliability. While the radiation effects on FPGAs have been widely studied, the impact of HLS configuration parameters and their sensitivity to thermal neutrons has not been fully assessed. This experiment evaluated the effects of thermal neutrons on the reliability of DNN accelerators created using Xilinx HLS tools, focusing on safety-critical applications. We also performed the same tests on the Chiplr facility to compare the results obtained at EMMA with atmospheric neutrons.

Experiment test report

1. Setup

We successfully evaluated multiple configurations of a DNN for image classification using the FINN HLS tool from Xilinx [1]. This tool allows us to configure the accelerator based on the specific DNN we intend to execute. In our experiments, we adjusted two key parameters: clock frequency and Frames Per Second (FPS). Table 1 presents the parameters we set for this experiment.

We conducted experiments for at least 3 hours for each configuration or until we reached a fluence of 10^{10} cm^{-2} . During the experiments, we assessed the DNNs running on Xilinx PYNQ Z2 FPGAs. Figure 1 shows the resource utilization of the PYNQ FPGA for each of the configurations evaluated at EMMA. Note that all the configs have similar resource usage of the FPGA, which can impact the cross-section of the accelerators.

Table 1: Tested configurations tested at EMMA and Chiplr

DNN and dataset	Frequency	FPS
ResNet with the CIFAR10 dataset	100MHz	10
		40
	150MHz	10
		40
	200MHz	40

Figure 1: Resource utilization of the evaluated configurations. Even if the accelerator's performance is set to be higher, resource utilization remains similar.

Figure 2 shows the hardware and software setups mounted at both the EMMA and Chiplr beamlines. The software component consists of Python scripts running on a host computer outside the beam room, specifically a software watchdog (main server). This watchdog monitors device activity and assists in recovering from potential device hangs or crashes.

When the FPGA is powered on, it continuously sends messages to the main server to indicate its operational status. This includes signaling that the DNN accelerator is active, notifying of any failures, or indicating a crash through the absence of messages. If the server detects that the FPGA has stopped responding within a designated timeframe, it will initiate a restart.

The FPGA consistently operates under the same DNN configuration. Each iteration of the DNN consists of classifying a batch of images from the CIFAR-10 dataset. After each iteration, the DNN's output is compared to a predetermined fault-free value. If discrepancies are computed in the DNN output, the FPGA will send the differences to the main server to be logged. The main server will then perform a power reboot on the FPGA, restarting the process. It is essential to emphasize that only errors in the DNN output will be considered in the failure rate analysis.

Figure 2: The hardware setup mounted at Chiplr and EMMA beamlines.

2. Preliminary results

During our experiments, we observed two types of events: (1) misclassifications, which occur when the TOP1 classification of the DNN is incorrect despite the DNN accelerator running to completion (silent data corruption, SDC), and (2) Detected Unrecoverable Errors (DUE), which happen when the main server stops receiving messages from the FPGA, requiring a reboot.

Figure 3 presents the cross-section for all the configurations evaluated at Chiplr and EMMA. The x-axis represents the DNN configuration (Frequency and FPS), while the y-axis shows the cross-section. We calculated the cross-section by dividing the number of events (misclassification or DUEs) by the fluence.

As anticipated, the cross-sections obtained at EMMA were significantly lower than those obtained at Chiplr. On average, the EMMA misclassification cross-section was $1.55 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2$, while the Chiplr cross-section was $3.85 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2$. This aligns with existing research, which indicates that thermal neutrons are expected to yield a lower failure rate than atmospheric neutrons [2].

Another interesting finding from the experiments is that the cross-sections across various configurations did not vary significantly. We attribute this consistency to the similarity in the resources used, as shown

in Figure 1. In fact, DNNs that utilize similar hardware resources may exhibit comparable cross-sections, as the workloads being executed are the same across all configurations.

Figure 3: Experimentally measured SDC and DUE Cross-sections for the multiple designs generated using the Xilinx FINN tool. Cross-sections were extracted using EMMA and Chiplr facilities.

We are preparing a final research paper to address specific points of the results and discuss the differences with other works that also used HLS to generate optimized accelerators for DNNs.

References

[1] Xilinx FINN Fast, Scalable Quantized Neural Network Inference on FPGAs, online: <https://github.com/Xilinx/finn>

[2] D. Oliveira *et al.*, "Thermal Neutrons: a Possible Threat for Supercomputers and Safety Critical Applications," *2020 IEEE European Test Symposium (ETS)*, Tallinn, Estonia, 2020

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

User feedback

Nothing to complain about.

EDMS NO.	REV.	VALIDITY
3312942	1.0	Released

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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